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ARISE Research Assessment Model:

A Framework for Pilot Implementation at the Institute of Economic Sciences

February 2026

Foreword

The ARISE research assessment model has been developed as a pilot framework to be implemented at the Institute of Economic Sciences, with the aim of testing, refining, and demonstrating a more responsible, transparent, qualitative and peer-review based approach to research assessment in the Republic of Serbia. While grounded in the specific institutional context of the Institute, the model is conceived as a scalable and transferable framework, intended to inform broader discussions and future reforms of research assessment across the Serbian research system.

Serbia's research assessment system is normatively developed but substantively indicator-driven, administrative, and context-blind. It produces formal measurability without learning, differentiation, or strategic steering. These structural limitations make the current model inadequate for contemporary scientific practice and clearly justify a transition toward a qualitative, peer-review-based, and context-sensitive approach aligned with European reform trajectories.

The ARISE pilot model responds to this need by introducing an assessment framework that combines structured self-assessment, external peer review, and the responsible use of quantitative indicators. Evaluation reports produced within the pilot are intended to support institutional development at the Institute of Economic Sciences, facilitate strategic dialogue, and generate evidence and experience that can inform future policy-oriented reforms at national level.

This document is intended to guide the pilot implementation of the ARISE assessment model at the Institute of Economic Sciences, providing a common reference for all actors involved in the process, including researchers, reviewers, and institutional leadership. At the same time, the document is written with a view to future dissemination, providing a reference point for other research-performing organizations and policymakers interested in adapting and applying the ARISE approach in different institutional contexts.

The guide first presents the overall assessment framework, including its objectives, core principles, assessment dimensions, and methodology. It then outlines the self-assessment process and supporting tools, followed by guidance for external peer reviewers, including rubrics, performance scales, and explanatory criteria. In this way, the document offers a coherent and operational understanding of the pilot assessment process, while laying the groundwork for potential broader application.

The evaluation methods presented in this guide are informed by international good practices in research assessment, comparative analysis of European assessment systems, and consultations with researchers and administrative staff at the Institute of Economic Sciences, as well as with members of a multidisciplinary Advisory Board, ensuring discipline-sensitive adjustments in the development of the ARISE model. The framework

is aligned with CoARA commitments for responsible research assessment, emphasizing qualitative peer judgment and the careful, contextual use of quantitative indicators.

This guide is deliberately designed as flexible and developmental, reflecting its pilot nature. It recognizes and allows for the recognition of diverse forms of research contribution, reflecting differences in scientific disciplines, institutional missions, and organizational capacities, while being developed within the specific context of the Institute of Economic Sciences and designed for adaptation across the Serbian research system. Within the pilot, the Institute of Economic Sciences is encouraged to apply the framework in a manner that is context-sensitive and focused on learning, rather than compliance.

The assessment process should be understood primarily as an opportunity for collective reflection, institutional learning, and continuous improvement. Insights and lessons derived from the pilot implementation are expected to inform the further refinement of the ARISE model and to contribute to the design of a future, more comprehensive research assessment framework at national level.

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1. Purpose and Scope of the Model

The ARISE research assessment model has been developed as part of the Advancing Research Assessment in Serbia: A Pilot Project for the Institute of Economic Sciences (ARISE) project, funded under the CoARA Boost Horizon Europe programme. The primary purpose of the model is to pilot a responsible, qualitative, peer-review based and context-sensitive approach to research assessment at the Institute of Economic Sciences (IES), in alignment with the commitments of the Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA).

The model responds to a recognised need for reform of research assessment practices in Serbia, where existing evaluation frameworks predominantly rely on quantitative indicators, such as publication counts, journal rankings, and citation-based metrics. While such indicators provide useful information, they often fail to adequately capture the quality, impact, diversity, and broader relevance of research contributions, particularly in the social sciences.

The ARISE model is designed as a unit-level assessment framework, shifting the focus from individual researchers to research teams. Its objective is not to rank research departments or impose sanctions, but to support learning, reflection, and strategic development within research units. The model places particular emphasis on qualitative peer review, narrative self-assessment, and contextualised evidence, while maintaining compatibility with existing national frameworks.

Importantly, the model is conceived as a pilot and developmental tool, not as a final or prescriptive solution. Through pilot implementation, feedback, and iterative refinement, the ARISE project aims to explore the feasibility, credibility, and acceptability of qualitative research assessment practices within the Serbian research system.

Policy and Reform Context

The development of the ARISE research assessment model takes place within a broader national and international reform context. At the national level, research assessment in Serbia is predominantly oriented towards the evaluation of individual researchers, primarily within procedures for appointment and promotion to scientific titles. These procedures are largely driven by quantitative indicators, which tend to incentivise hyper productivity, particularly through an emphasis on publication counts and the formal categorisation of publication venues. While elements of qualitative contribution are formally acknowledged, they are in practice assessed through proxy indicators, allowing only a limited evaluation of the actual quality, impact, and broader contribution of research activities. As a result, current assessment practices provide a narrow representation of research performance, with limited capacity to capture originality, societal relevance, or longer-term scientific contribution. While these mechanisms provide a degree of standardisation and transparency, they also generate well-documented limitations, including an overemphasis on volume rather than quality,

insufficient recognition of diverse research contributions, and limited sensitivity to disciplinary specificities, particularly in the social sciences.

At the international level, research assessment reform has gained significant momentum through initiatives such as the Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA) and the Declaration on Reforming Research assessment (DORA), which promote responsible, fair, and meaningful evaluation practices. CoARA and DORA encourage a shift away from narrow metric-based approaches towards qualitative, peer-based, and context-aware assessment models that better reflect the multifaceted nature of research activities and impacts.

Comparative insights from European research systems illustrate that reform does not require abrupt or disruptive change. Rather, gradual rebalancing combining quantitative evidence with qualitative judgement has proven both realistic and effective. The ARISE model draws on these experiences, aiming to translate international reform principles into a form that is feasible and legitimate within the Serbian institutional and policy environment.

Against this background, ARISE adopts a pilot-based approach, allowing experimentation, institutional learning, and dialogue with the research community before any consideration of broader application or scaling.

2. Guiding Principles of the Model

The ARISE research assessment model is guided by a set of core principles that reflect both international reform agendas and the specific institutional and national context in which the model is being developed. These principles inform the design of the assessment process, the choice of evidence, and the role of peer review.

1) Unit-level focus

The model shifts the unit of assessment from individual researchers to research departments. This approach recognises that research quality and impact are produced within collective environments shaped by leadership, collaboration, mentoring practices, and shared research strategies.

2) Primacy of qualitative peer review

Qualitative peer review constitutes the central evaluative mechanism of the model. Expert judgement, grounded in disciplinary knowledge and contextual understanding, is prioritised over purely metric-based evaluation.

3) Use of narrative and contextual evidence

Research departments are invited to reflect on their activities and achievements through structured narrative self-assessment. Quantitative indicators may be included as supporting evidence, but they do not determine assessment outcomes.

4) Developmental orientation

The model is explicitly developmental rather than punitive. Its purpose is to support learning, reflection, and improvement, not to rank departments or impose sanctions.

5) Transparency and procedural integrity

The assessment process is designed to be transparent, with clearly defined stages, roles, and criteria. Both departments and reviewers are provided with guidance to ensure consistency and fairness.

6) Alignment with CoARA principles

The model is aligned with internationally recognised principles of responsible research assessment, as promoted by CoARA, while remaining compatible with the Serbian research policy framework.

3. Core Values of Assessment

The ARISE research assessment model is structured around a set of core values that define what is considered meaningful and valuable research activity at the Institute of Economic Sciences.

These values were identified through a participatory process, including focus groups with researchers and consultations within the Institute and with the Advisory Board, and reflect both disciplinary/field specificities and international good practice.

The core values underpinning the model are:

- **Scientific quality and excellence**

This value emphasizes the pursuit of high-quality research characterized by originality, methodological rigor, coherence, and a meaningful contribution to the advancement of knowledge within relevant research area.

- **Strategic relevance and responsible project engagement**

This value highlights the importance of engaging in research projects that are strategically aligned with the Institute's priorities and relevant European research priorities, responsibly managed, and contributing to sustainable scientific development, rather than prioritising funding acquisition alone.

- **Sustainability of research capacities and careers**

This value focuses on strengthening long-term research capacities through mentoring, skills development, and support for researchers at different career stages, ensuring the continuity and resilience of the research environment.

- **Societal relevance and engagement**

This value recognizes research activities that engage with policy processes, public debate, and societal challenges, and that contribute to informed decision-making, innovation, and broader societal benefit.

- **Collaboration, integrity, and inclusive research culture**

This value promotes transparent and fair collaboration, responsible research practices, and an inclusive research culture that fosters trust, diversity, well-being, and shared responsibility within the research community.

- **International openness and cooperation**

This value underscores the importance of international collaboration, mobility, and participation in global research networks as a means to enhance research quality, visibility, and integration within the European and international research landscape.

These values form the basis for both the self-assessment process and the external peer review, ensuring coherence between how departments reflect on their work and how that work is evaluated.

4. Assessment Dimensions

Building on these core values, the ARISE model operationalizes research assessment through a limited number of assessment dimensions that capture both core research performance and broader, supporting research-related contributions. The dimensions are intentionally broad and qualitative in nature, allowing for contextual interpretation across different research fields and organizational units within the Institute.

The model distinguishes two core assessment dimensions, which reflect the central pillars of research performance, and four supporting dimensions, which capture complementary, developmental, and contextual aspects of research activity. This distinction reflects the principle that high-quality research publications and scientific outputs and strategically relevant research projects form the backbone of research assessment, while other dimensions provide essential support to research quality, sustainability, and impact.

Each dimension is assessed primarily through structured self-assessment narratives prepared at the department level, complemented by selected evidence and reviewed through external peer evaluation. Quantitative indicators may be used only as contextual information and are not applied in a mechanistic or aggregative manner.

The assessment dimensions are as follows:

Core assessment dimensions:

- **Research Publications and Scientific Outputs** - focusing on the quality, originality, and contribution of scientific outputs, with particular attention to selected publications and other significant forms of scientific output relevant to the field (e.g. journals, monographs, edited volumes, conferences) and their contribution to the advancement of knowledge within relevant disciplines/fields;
- **Research Projects and Strategic Relevance** - covering participation in competitive research projects and/or high-impact project proposals, success in attracting external funding, leadership roles, and alignment with institutional and national research priorities.

Supporting assessment dimensions:

- **Mentoring, Development and Lifelong Learning of Researchers** - addressing supervision of early-career researchers, mentoring practices, skills development, and contributions to building sustainable research capacities;
- **Societal, Policy, and Economic Engagement** - capturing research contributions that inform policymaking, address societal challenges, contribute to public debate, or support innovation and economic development;
- **Collaboration and Research Environment** - assessing teamwork, cross-departmental collaboration, leadership within research groups, and contributions to a supportive and inclusive research environment;
- **International Cooperation and Networking** - focusing on participation in international research networks, collaborative projects, mobility, and other forms of international scientific engagement.

Together, these dimensions provide a coherent framework for reflective self-assessment and qualitative peer review, supporting the developmental purpose of the ARISE model. The relative importance of individual dimensions and their weighting within the overall assessment are specified in a dedicated section of the model. Rather than producing rankings, the assessment aims to identify strengths, areas for improvement, and strategic opportunities for departments and the Institute as a whole.

5. Assessment Objectives, Process and Methodology

The ARISE research assessment model is designed as a qualitative, contextual, and developmental process, aligned with the principles of responsible research assessment and the objectives of institutional learning and improvement. The assessment pursues

three objectives: reflective analysis, continuous improvement, and strategic dialogue between researchers, department leadership, and institute management, aimed at strengthening shared understanding of research priorities, performance, and future development.

The assessment process combines structured self-assessment with external peer review, ensuring both internal reflection and independent evaluation. The process includes preparation of self-assessment reports, selection of an expert committee; document analysis; online and/or on-site visit and interviews; drafting of evaluation reports; validation and publication of final assessment reports.

1) Self-Assessment Process

The assessment process begins with a structured self-assessment report conducted at the department level. Departments are invited to reflect on their activities and performance in relation to the core values and assessment dimensions defined in the model. The self-assessment is narrative-based and focuses on qualitative descriptions supported by selected evidence, rather than comprehensive reporting of all outputs.

Departments are encouraged to highlight their main strengths, key achievements, challenges, and areas for improvement, considering disciplinary specificities and contextual factors. The self-assessment serves as a core input to the overall evaluation and as a tool for internal reflection and strategic discussion within the Institute.

2) Role of Quantitative Indicators

Quantitative indicators, such as publication counts, project funding volumes, or participation metrics, may be included in the self-assessment only as contextual information. Indicators are not used in a mechanistic or aggregative manner, nor are they combined into composite scores or rankings. Their role is to support qualitative judgment and to provide background information for peer reviewers, in line with CoARA commitments.

3) External Peer Review

Following the self-assessment phase, departments are evaluated through an external peer review process conducted in accordance with the principles of transparency, objectivity, scientific integrity, and contextualised assessment. Peer reviewers are selected based on their understanding of research assessment principles and familiarity with the relevant disciplinary and institutional context.

Independent external reviewers assess the self-assessment narratives and supporting evidence in relation to the defined assessment dimensions. The review is grounded in qualitative expert judgment, focusing on coherence, relevance, and alignment with the core values of the model. On this basis, reviewers assign dimension-level grades in accordance with the defined performance classes, accompanied by written justification.

While grades provide a structured and transparent expression of peer judgment, the review process does not involve direct comparison or ranking across departments. Grading serves a supportive and developmental function, complementing qualitative feedback and contributing to a holistic assessment outcome.

4) Feedback and Learning-Oriented Outcomes

The outcome of the assessment process is a structured assessment report combining qualitative peer review feedback with dimension-level grades assigned in accordance with the defined performance classes and weighting scheme. The report highlights key strengths, good practices, and areas where further development may be encouraged, supported by narrative justification provided by peer reviewers.

Grades are assigned at the level of individual assessment dimensions and are grounded in qualitative expert judgment informed by self-assessment and supporting evidence. While indicative aggregated profiles may be derived for analytical and developmental purposes, the assessment does not result in rankings or automatic punitive measures. The primary purpose of the assessment remains learning-oriented, supporting institutional reflection, strategic development, and continuous improvement.

6. Self-Assessment: Purpose, Scope and Process

Research departments are encouraged to approach the self-assessment exercise as an opportunity for collective reflection and institutional learning. The process should enable the research unit to analyse its activities and achievements over the previous two-year period (2024–2025), identifying its main strengths and accomplishments, as well as challenges, limitations, and areas requiring further development.

The outcomes of this reflective process are presented in a structured self-assessment report, prepared by departments in accordance with the ARISE assessment framework and the defined assessment dimensions. The self-assessment follows a common template, ensuring consistency while allowing departments to contextualise their narratives in line with their disciplinary profiles and institutional roles.

Where relevant, departments may describe research activities that span multiple dimensions, such as links between scientific excellence, knowledge transfer, innovation, or societal engagement, in an integrated manner, provided that contributions across the relevant dimensions remain clearly articulated.

The document prepared by the research department, together with its appendix and any supporting materials, constitutes the single self-assessment report submitted for evaluation and used by external peer reviewers as the primary basis for assessment.

To ensure clarity and usability for peer reviewers, the self-assessment report should be concise and proportionate in length and not exceeding 10 pages, excluding the appendix.

The objective is to produce a clear, coherent, and readable document that enables expert reviewers to gain a comprehensive understanding of the department's research activities, profile, and strategic orientation.

The balance between retrospective self-assessment and the presentation of future-oriented objectives and priorities may vary depending on the specific characteristics, maturity, and strategic focus of each department, provided that both elements are adequately addressed.

7. Principles of Peer Review and Use of Indicators

The ARISE research assessment model explicitly reinforces the central role of peer review as the primary method of evaluation. Expert judgment, informed by structured self-assessment and qualitative analysis, constitutes the core of the assessment process. The use of quantitative and bibliometric indicators is strictly supportive and can never replace the qualitative evaluation of research outputs.

The IES formally commits to ensuring that research assessment is based solely on the quality and relevance of the research evaluated. Evaluation outcomes are independent of the language of publication, the type of publication, or the venue in which the research is published, in line with principles of fairness, inclusiveness, and disciplinary diversity.

Peer review is conducted by the committee composed of two independent, external experts. Where appropriate to the characteristics of a given research area, peer review may be informed by selected international bibliometric data. However, such data are used exclusively as contextual information and do not determine evaluation outcomes.

For publications indexed in major international bibliometric databases (such as Web of Science and Scopus), reviewers may be provided with the following information for contextual purposes:

- the number of citations received as of a specified reference date;
- the number of self-citations associated with the publication;
- journal-level impact indicators, including metrics such as Cite Score, SJR, SNIP, Impact Factor, five-year Impact Factor, and Article Influence.

Where appropriate, and in line with disciplinary specificities, particularly in fields such as the humanities, research departments may also include selected research outputs classified under category M10 (monographs, monographic studies, and thematic edited volumes of international relevance). Such outputs are assessed primarily through qualitative peer judgment, focusing on originality, scholarly contribution, and relevance within the field, rather than through bibliometric indicators.

These indicators are made available to support informed expert judgment and to enhance transparency, but they are not applied mechanistically and are not used as proxies for

research quality. Altimetric indicators are not considered within the ARISE assessment model.

8. Use of Assessment Results and Institutional Learning

The use of assessment results is guided by a developmental logic and aligned with the Institute's mission and long-term strategic objectives.

Assessment results are used to:

- support strategic discussions at the department and Institute levels;
- identify strengths, good practices, and areas for further development;
- inform institutional planning, capacity-building measures, and internal support mechanisms;
- enhance transparency and shared understanding of research values within the Institute.

The qualitative feedback generated through the assessment process serves as a basis for dialogue between departments and Institute management. Rather than prescribing uniform solutions, the model allows departments to interpret feedback in light of their specific disciplinary profiles, resources, and strategic priorities.

Importantly, the ARISE model does not use assessment results to produce rankings or league tables, nor does it rely on scores for automatic or punitive decision-making. While the assessment includes dimension-level grades and indicative aggregated profiles, these are derived from qualitative peer judgment and are intended to support transparency, reflection, and structured feedback. The primary emphasis of the model remains on learning, improvement, and institutional development, fostering a culture of trust, responsibility, and informed judgment in research assessment.

The model is conceived as iterative and adaptable. Lessons learned from each assessment cycle, including feedback from researchers and peer reviewers, are used to refine assessment dimensions, processes, and supporting tools over time. In this way, research assessment becomes an integral part of organizational learning and institutional development.

9. Annex I: Self-Assessment Report Template

The self-assessment report template provides a structured framework to support departments in preparing narrative overview of their research activities and development in a consistent yet flexible manner. The template is designed to encourage reflection and qualitative description, while avoiding excessive administrative burden.

The self-assessment report **should not exceed 10 pages, excluding appendix.**

Quantitative indicators are to be provided exclusively as supporting information **in a dedicated appendix** to the self-assessment report. Their purpose is to provide contextual background for peer reviewers and to support qualitative judgment. Quantitative indicators should **not be embedded in the narrative sections** of the self-assessment and should not be used as proxies for research quality.

For each section of the self-assessment report, a set of guiding questions is provided to support reflection and facilitate a consistent and focused narrative. These questions are indicative and are not intended to be answered exhaustively.

1. Structure of the Self-Assessment Report

A. Department Profile and Context

- **Profile statement** - a concise narrative statement outlining the department's research identity, main scientific orientations, and distinctive features within the Institute and the broader research landscape.
- **Disciplinary and organizational context** - key characteristics of the field, size of the department, career stages of researchers, and relevant contextual factors.
- **Strategic orientation and recent developments** - main strategic priorities, changes, or developments during the assessment period

Guiding questions:

- ✓ *What is the department's main research profile and scientific orientation? (core research areas, disciplinary focus)*
- ✓ *What key contextual factors shape the department's research activities? (size, career stages of researchers, disciplinary specificities, organizational context)*
- ✓ *What distinguishes the department's role within the Institute and its broader research environment? (distinctive features, complementarities, or specific mandates)*
- ✓ *Have there been any significant changes or developments during the assessment period that are relevant for understanding the department's current profile?*

B. Research Publications and Scientific Outputs

- **Overview of the department's scientific publication and output profile during the assessment period** - a concise narrative overview of the department's main research themes, dominant types of scientific outputs, and disciplinary positioning. This section should describe publication patterns and other significant forms of scientific output relevant to the field (e.g. journals, monographs, edited volumes, conferences), without providing exhaustive lists.
- Selected scientific publications and outputs illustrating quality and originality - departments are expected to select **up to three (1-3)** representative scientific

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outputs produced during the assessment period. Depending on disciplinary practices, selected outputs may include peer-reviewed journal articles; monographs, monographic studies, or edited volumes; the organisation of major scientific conferences or scholarly events, where these constitute a substantial scientific output in terms of dissemination of research results, scholarly exchange, and contribution to the advancement of the field. The selection should be justified briefly, explaining why the chosen outputs are representative of the department's scientific profile and quality.

- **Explanation of scientific contribution and significance** - for each selected publication or scientific output, departments should provide a concise explanation of its scientific contribution. In the case of publications, this should address originality, methodological rigor, and contribution to the relevant field. In the case of scientific conferences or scholarly events, the explanation should focus on the scientific rationale and thematic relevance of the event; the department's role (e.g. initiator, lead organiser, scientific chair); the quality and profile of participating researchers (e.g. international scope); the role of the event in disseminating research results, generating scholarly feedback, and strengthening the department's visibility and positioning within the scientific community. The emphasis should remain on substance, quality, and scientific significance, rather than on quantitative indicators or bibliometric measures.

Guiding questions:

- ✓ *What characterises the department's scientific publication and output profile during the assessment period? (main research themes, dominant types of outputs, publication patterns, and disciplinary context, without listing all outputs)*
- ✓ *Which 1–3 scientific publications or other key scientific outputs best illustrate the quality and originality of the department's research? (brief justification for the selection)*
- ✓ *How do the selected publications demonstrate originality, methodological rigor, and contribution to knowledge in the relevant field?*
- ✓ *What is the scientific significance of these outputs within their disciplinary context? (short, medium, or long-term contribution, as appropriate)*
- ✓ *In the case of scientific conferences or scholarly events, how did the department contribute to their scientific design, organisation, and academic quality, and what role did these outputs play in dissemination, scholarly feedback, and visibility within the field?*
- ✓ *How do the selected publications and outputs reflect the department's broader research strategy and the coherence of its research agenda?*

C. Research Projects and Strategic Relevance

- **Overview of participation in competitive research projects and funding schemes** - a concise analytical overview of the department's engagement in competitive research projects during the assessment period. This section should

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describe the main types of projects and funding schemes (e.g. national, international, competitive calls), overall trends in project participation, and the role of project-based research in supporting the department's research agenda. Where relevant, departments may also briefly reflect on significant project proposals submitted during the assessment period, particularly in cases when low success rates or structural features of competitive calls limit funding outcomes. This overview should focus on strategic orientation rather than providing exhaustive lists.

- **Selected research projects and project proposals illustrating strategic relevance** - departments are expected to select **up to three (1–3) key research projects** key research projects or, where appropriate, high-quality project proposals developed during the assessment period. Selected items should be chosen based on their scientific relevance, strategic importance for the department, and alignment with the department's research priorities and thematic focus. The selection should be briefly justified. In the case of project proposals that were not funded, departments should explain their scientific ambition, strategic relevance, and contribution to the development of the department's research profile.
- **Explanation of roles in projects and strategic contribution** - for each selected project or project proposal, departments should briefly describe their role (e.g. coordination, leadership, or partnership) and explain how the project contributes to the department's scientific profile, capacity building, institutional priorities, or longer-term strategic objectives of the Institute. The emphasis should be placed on strategic intent, scientific quality, and developmental contribution, rather than funding outcomes alone.

Guiding questions:

- ✓ *What are the department's main types of research projects and funding schemes during the assessment period? (contextual overview of project engagement, not an exhaustive list)*
- ✓ *Which 1–3 research projects or high-quality project proposals best illustrate the department's strategic priorities and developmental trajectory?*
- ✓ *What roles does the department play in these projects or project proposals (coordination, leadership, partnership), and why are these roles strategically and scientifically significant?*
- ✓ *How do the selected projects or project proposals contribute to the department's scientific profile, capacity building, or longer-term strategic objectives of the Institute?*
- ✓ *How are project activities and project proposals linked to other research outputs, researcher development, or future research directions?*

D. Mentoring, Development and Lifelong Learning of Researchers

- **Overview of mentoring, researcher development and lifelong learning practices** – a concise analytical overview of the department's approach to mentoring young researchers and early-career researchers (up to five years after

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completion of the PhD) on the one hand and lifelong learning practices and activities during the assessment period on the other hand. This section should describe the main forms of supervision and mentoring, capacity-building practices supporting the acquisition of scientific, methodological, and transferable skills, measures facilitating career development, as well as general approaches to supporting researchers at different career stages. It should not provide a list of individual supervisees or activities.

- **Selected examples illustrating mentoring and development practices** - departments are expected to select **up to three (1-3) representative examples** that illustrate their mentoring and researcher development practices during the assessment period. Examples may include supervision of doctoral or early-career researchers, structured mentoring schemes, training initiatives, or capacity-building activities. The selection should be briefly justified.
- **Explanation of contribution to researcher's development and research environment** - for each selected example, departments should briefly explain how the activity contributed to researcher development, skills acquisition, career progression, promoting equal opportunities, integration of new researchers or the creation of a supportive and inclusive research environment. Where relevant, attention may be given to sustainability, inclusiveness, and longer-term impact.

Guiding questions:

- ✓ *How are early-career researchers supervised and trained?*
- ✓ *What career development, inclusion, and capacity-building measures exist?*
- ✓ *How do these mentoring and development practices contribute to a supportive and inclusive research environment?*
- ✓ *What evidence suggests that these practices have a positive impact on researcher development or career progression?*

E. Societal, Policy and Economic Engagement

Important note: This section focuses on meaningful engagement and potential pathways to impact. Departments are not expected to demonstrate measurable impact outcomes, particularly where such impacts materialize over longer timeframes.

- **Overview of societal and policy engagement activities** - concise overview of the department's engagement with policy-makers, industry, civil society, or other societal actors during the assessment period. This section should describe the main forms and areas of engagement, without providing an exhaustive list of activities.
- **Selected examples illustrating societal or policy engagement** - departments are expected to select **up to three (1-3) representative examples** of societal or policy engagement undertaken during the assessment period. Examples may include contributions to policy processes, advisory roles, collaboration with industry or public institutions, participation in public debate, round tables or activities addressing societal challenges. The selection should be briefly justified.

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- **Explanation of contribution and pathways to impact** - for each selected example, departments should explain the nature of their contribution and, where relevant, describe plausible pathways to impact. This may include short, medium, or long-term effects on policy development, public understanding, professional practice, or societal challenges. Evidence of engagement or uptake may be provided where available, without requiring proof of impact.

Guiding questions:

- ✓ *What forms of engagement with policymakers, industry, or societal actors has the department undertaken during the assessment period?*
- ✓ *Which 1–3 examples best illustrate the department’s societal or policy engagement, and why were they selected?*
- ✓ *What was the nature of the department’s contribution in each selected case? (e.g. expertise provided, analysis conducted, dialogue facilitated)*
- ✓ *Where relevant, what plausible pathways to impact can be identified? (short, medium, or long-term effects on policy, practice, or societal challenges)*
- ✓ *How does societal and policy engagement relate to the department’s broader research agenda or strategic priorities?*

F. Collaboration and Research Environment

- **Overview of teamwork and collective research practices** - concise analytical overview of how teamwork and collective research activities are organised and supported within the department during the assessment period. This section should highlight internal collaboration practices, cooperation across departments, and mechanisms that support collective research work and knowledge exchange within the Institute.
- **Selected examples illustrating teamwork and collective practices** - departments are expected to select **up to three (1–3) representative examples** that illustrate effective teamwork, with an explicit indication of the number of team members involved in each example, in order to demonstrate the level of engagement and participation of researchers within the department, as well as cooperation across departments, or collective research practices. Examples may include shared research initiatives, joint scientific activities, internal working groups, coordinated research efforts, or mechanisms supporting collaboration and knowledge exchange. The selection should be briefly justified.
- **Contribution to the functioning and development of the research environment** - for each selected example, departments should explain how the activity contributes to the effective functioning, governance, and continuous development of the research environment. This may include contributions to leadership, shared scientific activities, academic culture, institutional cohesion, research integrity, or inclusiveness.

Guiding questions:

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- ✓ *How are teamwork and collective research activities organised and supported within the department and across departments within the Institute? How many researchers are involved in these teams or collective activities?*
- ✓ *What mechanisms support cooperation across departments and facilitate knowledge exchange within the research environment?*
- ✓ *Which 1–3 examples best illustrate effective teamwork or cooperation across departments, and why were they selected?*
- ✓ *How do these practices contribute to the effective functioning, governance, and development of the research environment?*
- ✓ *How does teamwork foster academic culture, research integrity, diversity, and researcher well-being?*
- ✓ *What forms of leadership or shared responsibility support collaboration and institutional cohesion within the department and the Institute?*

G. International Cooperation and Networking

Important note: Quantitative information related to cooperation and networking (e.g. number of international partners, mobility periods, joint publications, projects) should be provided in the appendix with quantitative indicators and should not be included in the narrative sections.

- **Overview of international research cooperation and networking** - a concise analytical overview of the department's engagement in international research cooperation during the assessment period. This section should highlight participation in research networks, collaborative initiatives, and partnerships with other research-performing organisations, with particular attention to international engagement and global visibility. It should not include an exhaustive list of collaborations.
- **Selected examples illustrating cooperation and networking activities** - departments are expected to select **up to three (1–3) representative examples of international cooperation and networking**. Examples may include participation in international research networks, joint research projects, co-publications with international partners, researcher mobility schemes, or structured partnerships with foreign institutions. The selection should be briefly justified.
- **Strategic importance of national and international engagement** - for each selected example, departments should explain the strategic relevance of the cooperation activity, including its contribution to research quality, capacity development, visibility, and the integration of the department and the Institute within the European research area.

Guiding questions:

- ✓ *What forms of international research cooperation and networking has the department engaged in during the assessment period?*
- ✓ *Which 1–3 examples best illustrate meaningful cooperation or networking activities, and why were they selected?*

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- ✓ *How do these activities contribute to the international visibility and positioning of the department's research?*
- ✓ *What role do mobility, joint publications, or international projects play in strengthening research quality and capacity development?*
- ✓ *How does international engagement support the department's strategic objectives and its integration within the European research area?*

H. Reflections and Future Development

- **Key strengths and achievements** - concise synthesis of the main strengths and achievements identified by the department during the assessment period, drawing on the analysis presented in the previous sections. This section should not introduce new evidence but rather reflect on recurring strengths and positive patterns.
- **Main challenges and areas for improvement** - a critical reflection on the main challenges, limitations, or areas requiring further development. This may include scientific, organisational, or capacity-related issues, as well as external constraints affecting the department's work.
- **Planned actions and strategic priorities for the next period** - based on the reflection above, departments should outline their key strategic priorities and planned actions for the forthcoming period. These may include scientific objectives, organisational or governance-related developments, capacity-building measures, or initiatives aimed at enhancing research quality, societal relevance, visibility, or sustainability.

Guiding questions:

- ✓ *What are the main strengths and achievements of the department during the assessment period, as identified through the self-assessment?*
- ✓ *What key challenges, limitations, or areas for improvement have emerged from the analysis?*
- ✓ *What lessons can be drawn from the assessment process to support future development?*
- ✓ *What are the department's main strategic priorities and planned actions for the forthcoming period?*
- ✓ *How do the proposed priorities and actions align with available resources and the broader national and international research environment?*

2. Portfolio (optional)

Departments may, **on an optional basis**, attach a portfolio of selected achievements to the appendix of the self-assessment report in order to provide additional references or illustrative materials.

The portfolio serves as a **supplementary qualitative element** of the evaluation and may include a limited selection of representative outputs that help illustrate the unit's

scientific activities and potential impact, such as publications or books, innovative projects, partnerships, policy contributions, start-ups, or notable training initiatives.

The portfolio should be limited to a **maximum of five (5) selected items**. The objective is to provide a **focused and meaningful selection**, rather than a comprehensive list of activities or outputs.

Annex II: Scoring Framework / Assessment Methodology and Peer Review Rubrics

1. General Principles of Peer Review

Peer review within the ARISE assessment model is based on expert qualitative judgment, informed by structured self-assessment narratives and selected evidence. Quantitative grades and weights are introduced as a transitional and supportive mechanism, aimed at ensuring consistency, transparency, and acceptance of the assessment process during the early phases of reform.

Grades do not replace peer judgment and must always be accompanied by a qualitative justification. No automatic ranking or sanctioning follows from the results.

2. Classes of Merit

Each assessment dimension is assigned to one qualitative performance class, based on peer reviewers' holistic judgment of the evidence and narrative provided in the self-assessment report.

Performance class	Description	Coefficient
Exceptional	Outstanding quality, significance and relevance	1.0
Excellent	Very high quality and clear, well-substantiated contribution	0.8
Standard	Adequate quality, meets expected standards	0.5
Sufficient	Limited but acceptable contribution	0.2
Low relevance / Unacceptable	Insufficient quality or relevance	0.0

Grades are assigned after qualitative evaluation and must be justified in written peer review comments.

3. Assessment Dimensions and Relative Weighting

The following assessment dimensions operationalise the core values of the ARISE model. The model distinguishes between core assessment dimensions, which capture the central

pillars of research performance, and supporting assessment dimensions, which reflect complementary, developmental, and contextual aspects of research activity.

The core dimensions focus on research publications and scientific outputs and strategically relevant research projects and therefore carry greater relative importance within the overall assessment framework. The supporting dimensions provide essential contextual insight into how research quality is sustained, developed, and connected to broader institutional, societal, and international environments.

The dimensions are assigned different relative weights to reflect institutional priorities and the specific objectives of the pilot phase. This differentiated weighting approach is intended to support a gradual and contextualised transition towards a more balanced and qualitative research assessment model.

Dimension	Weight
Core dimension	
Research publications and scientific outputs	25%
Research projects and strategic relevance	25%
Supporting dimension	
Mentoring and development and lifelong learning of researchers	15%
Societal, policy impact and economic engagement	15%
Collaboration and research environment	10%
International cooperation	10%
Total	100%

The relative weights assigned to the assessment dimensions sum to 100%.

4. Peer Review Rubrics

The peer review rubrics provide structured guidance for peer reviewers on how each assessment dimension should be evaluated. For each dimension, the rubrics outline the key evaluation criteria that should inform reviewers' qualitative judgment, as well as grading guidance linked to the performance classes.

Specifically, the rubrics:

- clarify the aspects of research activity to be considered within each dimension;
- support a holistic and contextualised assessment, rather than checklist-based scoring;
- provide interpretative guidance for assigning a performance class (e.g. Exceptional, Excellent, Standard) based on the overall strength, coherence, and relevance of the evidence presented;
- ensure consistency and transparency across reviews, while allowing reviewers to exercise expert judgment.

The rubrics do not introduce additional sub-scores or numerical calculations. Instead, they function as a qualitative reference framework that links the self-assessment narrative to the final assessment at the level of each dimension.

1. Research Publications and Scientific Outputs

Scientific publications are assessed holistically, taking into account originality, methodology, and scientific impact, in line with CoARA commitments.

Dimension 1: Research Publications and Scientific Outputs	
Weight	25%
Evaluation criteria	<p>Originality - The ability of the research publication or other scientific output (e.g. organization of major scientific conferences) to introduce new ideas, interpretations, theoretical approaches, or methods, including the transfer of methods from other disciplines where relevant. In the case of scientific conferences, originality refers to the novelty and coherence of the scientific concept, thematic framing, and contribution to advancing scholarly debate in the field.</p>
	<p>Methodology / Scholarly criterion - The clarity and rigor of research objectives, the appropriate use of literature, coherence between methods and results, transparency of procedures, and, where applicable, reproducibility and access to data. For conferences or scholarly events, this criterion refers to scientific quality and credibility of the event, including: the quality and relevance of the presented papers or contributions; the scientific standing and expertise of participating researchers; the presence and role of international contributors and speakers; the quality, relevance, and academic reputation of keynote or plenary speakers; the composition and credibility of scientific and organising committees; the involvement and reputation of partner or co-organising institutions; the existence and rigor of peer review, selection, or quality assurance procedures; and the overall scholarly coherence and the extent to which the programme advances or critically engages with key debates in the field</p>
	<p>Scientific impact - The potential or actual contribution of the research publication or scientific output to the advancement of knowledge at the national and/or international level, in the short, medium, or long term. For conferences or scholarly events, scientific impact</p>

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	may be reflected in their role in disseminating research results, generating scholarly feedback, fostering scientific exchange, and strengthening the visibility and positioning of the department within the relevant research community.
Grading guidance	Exceptional (1.0): Outstanding originality, methodological rigor, and high scientific impact; represents leading or exemplary contributions in the field, including internationally recognised publications or high-level scientific conferences with clear influence on scholarly debate.
	Excellent (0.8): Very strong contribution with clear originality and solid methodology or quality; demonstrates significant impact and recognition within the discipline or research community.
	Standard (0.5): Adequate scientific quality; meets disciplinary standards but with limited originality or impact.
	Sufficient (0.2): Limited contribution; acceptable but modest in scope, depth or scientific impact.
	Low relevance/Unacceptable (0.0): Insufficient quality, rigor, or relevance; does not meet basic scholarly standards.

2. Research Projects and Strategic Relevance

This dimension assesses engagement in competitive research projects and their strategic relevance.

Dimension 2: Research Projects and Strategic Relevance	
Weight	25%
Evaluation criteria	Success in securing competitive research funding
	Leadership or coordination roles in projects and/ or high-impact project proposals¹
	Strategic relevance of projects and project proposals for the department and the Institute
	Contribution to research capacity and sustainability
Grading guidance	Exceptional (1.0): Sustained success in competitive funding and/or a strong portfolio of high-impact project proposals, strong leadership or coordination roles, and high strategic relevance

¹ High-impact project proposals refer to competitive proposals submitted to reputable national or international funding schemes that were positively evaluated, reached advanced evaluation stages, or are clearly aligned with strategic research priorities, even if not ultimately funded.

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	Excellent (0.8): Strong participation in competitive projects and/or well-developed, strategically relevant project proposals with clear relevance and meaningful roles
	Standard (0.5): Regular participation in projects or proposal submission, demonstrating adequate competitiveness and alignment with the department's research agenda.
	Sufficient (0.2): Limited or occasional engagement in research projects or project proposals, with modest strategic relevance
	Low relevance/Unacceptable (0.0): Absence of meaningful, relevant, or credible engagement in research projects or competitive project proposal activity

3. Mentoring, Development and Lifelong Learning of Researchers

This dimension captures contributions to the development of researchers and long-term research capacity.

Dimension 3: Mentoring, Development and Lifelong Learning of Researchers	
Weight	15%
Evaluation criteria	Mentoring and supervision of early-career researchers
	Skills development and capacity-building activities
	Contribution to inclusive and supportive research environments.
Grading guidance	Exceptional (1.0): Strategic, systematic, and exemplary mentoring and development practices that are well embedded in the department's activities
	Excellent (0.8): Strong and consistent mentoring, skills development, and capacity-building practices
	Standard (0.5): Adequate mentoring and development practices that meet expected standards
	Sufficient (0.2): Limited, informal, or ad hoc mentoring and development activities
	Low relevance/Unacceptable (0.0): Absence of meaningful or credible mentoring, development, or lifelong learning practices

4. Societal, policy and Economic Engagement

This dimension assesses engagement beyond academia and contributions to societal or policy processes.

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Dimension 4: Societal, policy and Economic Engagement	
Weight	15%
Evaluation criteria	Relevance of engagement to societal, policy, or economic challenges
	Credibility and appropriateness of engagement activities
	Clarity of pathways to impact
Grading guidance	Exceptional (1.0): Sustained, credible and high-impact engagement influencing policy, societal and/or economic processes/outcomes
	Excellent (0.8): Clear, well-documented engagement activities with meaningful societal, policy, and/or economic relevance
	Standard (0.5): Relevant engagement activities with limited scope
	Sufficient (0.2): Occasional or weakly articulated engagement activities
	Low relevance/Unacceptable (0.0): Absence of meaningful or relevant societal, policy, or economic engagement

5. Collaboration and Research Environment

This dimension captures collaboration, leadership, and institutional engagement.

Dimension 5: Collaboration and Research Environment	
Weight	10%
Evaluation criteria	Teamwork and collaborative research practices
	Leadership within research groups or across departments
	Contribution to institutional functioning, academic culture, and the research environment
Grading guidance	Exceptional (1.0): Exemplary leadership and a strong, sustained contribution to a positive and inclusive research environment
	Excellent (0.8): Effective collaboration practices and clear leadership contributions
	Standard (0.5): Adequate teamwork and contribution to the functioning of the research environment
	Sufficient (0.2): Limited or occasional contribution to teamwork or the research environment

	Low relevance/Unacceptable (0.0): Absence of meaningful or credible contribution to collaboration or the research environment
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6. Networking and International Cooperation

This dimension assesses international engagement, visibility and research networking.

Dimension 6: Networking and International Cooperation	
Weight	10%
Evaluation criteria	Participation in international research networks
	International collaborations and researcher mobility
	Contribution to international visibility and recognition within the European Research Area
Grading guidance	Exceptional (1.0): Leadership roles in international research networks and sustained, high-impact international cooperation
	Excellent (0.8): Strong and strategically relevant international collaboration and visibility
	Standard (0.5): Regular and consistent international engagement
	Sufficient (0.2): Limited or occasional international activity
	Low relevance/Unacceptable (0.0): Absence of meaningful or relevant international engagement

5. Use of Scores

Scores derived from performance classes and weights are used to:

- support structured feedback;
- identify strengths and areas for development;
- inform strategic discussion at department and Institute level.

Scores are not used to produce rankings, league tables, or automatic decisions.

6. Site Visit and Interviews

The site visit is conducted by an expert committee composed of two independent foreign peer reviewers, selected on the basis of their experience in research assessment, and familiarity with international good practices, as well as the relevant disciplinary and institutional context.

As part of the site visit, the expert committee conducts interviews with the Institute's leadership, researchers, doctoral candidates, and support staff. Dedicated closed sessions

are organised to allow the committee to synthesise the evidence collected and formulate preliminary assessment conclusions

7. Final Assessment Report Structure

The final assessment report prepared by the expert committee is structured to provide a clear, coherent, and balanced overview of the evaluation findings. It includes the following elements:

- **Executive Summary** - A concise synthesis of the main findings, overall assessment, and key recommendations.
- **Context and Positioning of the Department** - A brief description of the mission, research profile, and institutional context relevant to the assessment.
- **Assessment by Dimension** - A structured analysis for each assessment dimension, which is directly grounded in the core values identified through a participatory process, highlighting key strengths, areas for improvement, and targeted recommendations.
- **Overall Evaluation and Performance Classes** - An integrated overview of the assessment results, including the performance class assigned to each dimension and the overall assessment.
- **Strategic Recommendations** - Forward-looking recommendations aimed at supporting institutional development, research quality, and strategic alignment.
- **Annexes and Supporting Evidence** - Any additional materials referenced by the expert committee in support of the assessment.